

THE SACRED NARCO— PSYCHOACTIVE PLANTS IN ANCIENT CIVILIZATION: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF NYMPHAEA CAERULEA (EGYPTIAN WATER LILY) FLOWER; ANALYSIS FROM PHARMACOLOGICAL TO MEDICINAL PERSPECTIVE FOR FUTURE APPLICATION.

¹*Ayishath Mufeedha*

Affiliation: [International Academy of Science]

Secondary Affiliations: American School, [Columbia University Vagelos College of Physicians and Surgeons, USA]

Researcher Based in: (Kuwait)

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ayxedal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Nymphaea (*Nauchali* var. *Caerulea*) is a plant that was once abundant on the Nile Delta. It is a rare type of water lily found in African and Asian regions. According to several studies, art depiction of the blue lotus flower was reported on Egyptian papyri and tombs from the 14th century B.C. It held a great cultural and religious significance within ancient civilization, in which ancient Egypt had the portrayal of it among multiple locations at various times throughout the history, which later went on as folklore or mythological tale. This study investigates and discuss its common use as a "traditional drug/ ingredient" in various rituals and examines its role to cure a variety of diseases. Additionally, investigates its role into some of the other cultures, such as (Mesoamerican, Persian, and Asian) that had the use of *nymphaea* species and related plants. Given the significance of this plant in Ancient Civilization, warranted further exploration and investigation of the use of it in modern times, its pharmaceutical properties, compounds and the link to several modern diseases and side effects. The main aim of this article includes; providing a comprehensive overview of its chemical properties, pharmacological activities, the underlying regulatory and legality mechanisms, hence discovering new potential for therapeutic use. This paper could guide researchers come to their conclusions about the *Nymphaea Caerulea* flower and hinder for further use of this plant.

KEYWORDS

Ancient Egypt, alkaloids, blue lotus, drugs, ethnobotany, flavonoids, historiography, Maya, *Nymphaea Caerulea*, Opium poppy, *Papaver Somniferum*, phytomedicine, rituals, water lily.

INTRODUCTION

The word "narcotic" originally referred to a range of substances that dulled the senses and relieved the pain; it is derived from the Greek word "stupor". Even though all drugs are still referred to as "narcotics," the term is now limited to opium, its derivatives, and their semi-synthetic equivalents (Udoumoh, 2024). Since centuries, the constant and continues use of botanical plants raised through (Trovato, 2017), which eventually led to the creation of modern medicines to further develop drug-discovery (Yuan et al., 2016). According to the World Health Organization (WHO Global Traditional Medicine Centre), around 88% of countries use herbal medicine (Oladimeji Ewumi, 2022). It is estimated that 80% of world population rely on traditional herbal medicine for primary health care (Woo et al., 2012). The prevalence of substance use disorders (SUDs) among individuals with opioid use disorder (OUD) is alarmingly high, much like the soaring of substance use disorder with 59.5% (95% CI: 49.1–69.5%) struggling with a comorbid addiction. Cocaine use disorder is present in 30.5% (95% CI: 23.0–38.7%), whilst alcohol use disorder in 27.1% (95% CI: 24.4–30.0%), and cannabis use disorder in 22.7% (95% CI: 19.0–26.6%). This highly highlights the

complex nature of addiction, where opioids often aren't the only substance in play with substances like cocaine, alcohol, and cannabis that are commonly used alongside. Opioid use disorders, are usually characterized by intense cravings, loss of control, and debilitating withdrawal symptoms (Santo et al., 2024).

On November 29, 1922, in Valley of the Kings, when Tutankhamun's tomb (King Tut) was opened actual dried blue lotus flowers and numerous artifacts related to blue lotus preserved with the pharaoh were found (Egypt Museum, 2022), (Hamza, 2024). The link between this flower and perfumes is also visible, the god Nefertum who is a deity of perfumes and the sacred lotus that represented Tutankhamun (Agata Ulanowska et al., 2018). Studies suggest the Blue Nile Flower was already used in a shamanic context before the rise of the pharaohs (Keppel Hesselink, 2018). *Nymphaea Caerulea* blooms for three consecutive days, which held extreme symbolic cultural significance for the ancient Egyptians. The flower opens in the morning and closes at noon, aligning with the sun's glory, Ra. This cycle is associated to the deities Osiris, Horus, and the Pharaoh, emphasizing its spiritual cycle and significance in the perspective of life, death, and

rebirth. The flower contains a narcotic nectar known for its lethal effects on pollinators, indicating its powerful biochemical properties. This narcotic property is important in the context of shamanistic practices, where it may have been used to induce trance states. It was portrayed in ancient Egyptian art and texts as a symbol of life and resurrection, often associated with the god Osiris as previously said, and its depiction in funerary contexts suggests its role in rituals aimed at achieving transcendence and healing. The same paper clarifies that *Nymphaea Caerulea* is often confused with the lotus (*Nelumbo nucifera*), which was nonexistent to ancient Egypt until it was brought there by the Assyrians around 700 B.C. (Emboden, 1989), (Meyer et al., 1981).

The psychoactive properties of *Nymphaea* species, including their use in inducing altered states of consciousness, suggest that they may have been utilized for their calming and euphoric effects in rituals, as well as in many other occasions and the historical context implies that its psychoactive effects could have contributed to a sedative-like experience during rituals (W. A. Emboden, 1982). The information from the past studies points to the fact that the Ancient Egyptians had knowledge of hallucinogenic substances, as demonstrated by their utilization of drugs like mescaline, in rituals to enhance spiritual experiences and healing practices. These substances were part of sacred dramas or magical religious dances performed to invoke spiritual powers and facilitate healing. The article describes the continuation of these practices in the modern 'Zar dance,' in which women believed to be possessed by spirits gather to participate in traditional music and dance, aiming to expel the spirits (Nasser, 1987). The use of *Nymphaea Caerulea* in ancient Egyptian medicine reflects a broader trend of integrating local flora with foreign ideas as well, as seen in the evolving interpretations recorded by their scholars. This practice influenced later Greek and Roman medical traditions, highlighting the significance of Egyptian herbal knowledge. The blue lotus, often associated with the 'Eye of Horus', was symbolically linked to healing and protection in medical and spiritual rituals ("Vol. 59, No. 2, Apr., 2000 of Journal of Near Eastern Studies on JSTOR," n.d.). Additionally, the plant is known for its rich concentration of narcotic alkaloids, and as stated, played a significant role in ancient Egyptian religious and therapeutic practices. Its psychoactive properties were likely implemented to induce altered states of consciousness, facilitating spiritual experiences and connections with the divine. Symbolically, the blue water lily was associated with life, death, and rebirth, notoriously in funerary contexts, as evidenced by its frequent depiction in tomb art and religious texts (Book of the Dead). The plant's integration with other ritualistic elements, such as the poppy, shows its importance in rituals aimed at guaranteeing successful transitions to the afterlife, reflecting a complex insight on botany within ancient Egyptian spirituality and medicine (Christie, 2021).

This study aims to examine and review to showcase the traditional significance of *Nymphaea Caerulea* (blue lily of the Nile) in ancient civilization, how it played particularly focusing on Ancient Egypt. It will also compare the sacred water lily to those plants with comparable qualities in other civilization, and its properties or uses, link to their modern medical applications, and pharmacological properties. Additionally, the study will explore what potential do these plants hold for future therapeutic use. As the studies on *Nymphaea Caerulea* was seen to be limited, it required an urge to look through it for various possible medical uses. This question is both focused and specific, aiming to uncover the connections between ancient practices and current medical knowledge and its potential uses. Also, will be investigating any new details on the plant and propose the findings. By examining the active pharmacological compounds such as apomorphine and nuciferine claimed to be found in the blue lily and similar in other plants like opium poppy, this review will explore their roles in treating conditions or diseases such as the only known use for the plant to be for a 'disease', which has been signaled since the time of Anderson, when used it on for the treatment in tremor of paralysis agitans (ie., PD), due to the presence connected to apomorphine (Lanska, 2009), (Auffret et al., 2018). This study will intend to explore its potential use and connection to new diseases like Alzheimer's, link to Leukemia, cell studies, neurological conditions and several others, evidencing with past literature studies done. In short, *Nymphaea Caerulea*; its pharmacological properties, similarities to other plants, potential link and treatment towards the modern medical conditions.

METHODS

This study followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, and an analysis was conducted (Figure 1), looking through multiple literature describing the association between the ancient medical practices and the controversy behind the tale of *Nymphaea Caerulea* flower stood out the most, as the previous knowledge on this was quite substantial, by watching the documentary on the blue lotus of ancient Egypt, it has guided to find specific keywords associated with the plant. Finding connections or gaps between the ancient and the modern, as well as demonstrating how everything is related, such as how modern medical procedures are influenced by their ancient counterparts, and demonstrating how everything started with ancient practices, because that's what can be taken away from all of it, as it is all interlinked. This factor was taken into consideration after reading about studies involving ancient medical studies and papyrus in Greece and Egypt, even though they had rituals, magics, and more, similar in most of the practices, it had mentions of specific plants inducing aphrodisiac and hallucination effects, modern drug has similar features. This study considered how today's solution is viewing it as medicine

and healing rather than spiritual or magical than in the ancient times.

An investigative search throughout the internet databases such as PubMed and Google Scholar were carried out, secondly following up with secondary databases such as academia and research gate, and lastly, an extensive search via web browser.

A series of targeted searches were conducted across various databases to gather comprehensive data on *Nymphaea lotus* and its relevance in ancient Egypt. The search terms included "Nymphaea lotus in ancient Egypt" and "Water lily nymphomaniac lotus" in Google Scholar, focusing on the historical and botanical aspects of the plant. Searches for "Papaveraceae in Egypt" and "Ingredients used in Nymphaea lotus in ancient Egypt" were performed via Google to identify relevant contextual and botanical data. Specific queries in Google Scholar, such as "Nymphaea lotus and apomorphine," showed a number of results, while PubMed searches for "Nymphaea lotus and apomorphine" and "Nymphaea Caerulea" provided additional insights with few results, respectively. Searches for "Nuciferine and apomorphine" on PubMed and "Drugs in ancient Egypt" in Google Scholar complemented the research. Additionally, terms like "Water lily in ancient Egypt schematic" and "Chromones in Nymphaea Caerulea" were used to obtain schematic and chemical information. Furthermore, "Researchers studying on blue lotus Nymphaea Caerulea" was searched to identify ongoing studies and expert contributions. And lastly, titles from papers found through PubMed was re-applied and searched through again, resulting in around (n=87,500) new results for the literature extraction. Several studies were eliminated due to the irrelevance of the plant, as there were plants whose names began with "Nymphaea." However, later the studies were carefully once again read, analyzed and selected based on proper guidelines and inclusivity.

Figure 1: Process of evaluation for the studies.

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for new systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of *Nymphaea Caerulea*

The term "lotus" was originally used by the Greeks to describe a white-water lily (*N. lotus*), and afterwards the blue water lily (*N.C*) (figure 2) was given the same name by Athenaeus (*Nouchali var. caerulea*) (Prigioniero, 2020). According to a study, the Nymphaeaceae family has 69 species with 44 species falling under *Nymphaea*. The Nymphaeales families are aligned by (Hydatellaceae, Cabombaceae, Nymphaeaceae) all including around 87 species, they are together termed as Water lily order (Xiong et al., 2023). The flowers bloom from September to February and, when fully open, form a star-shaped pattern about 15–20 cm in diameter. Another study reveals that the flowers close in the afternoon after opening in the morning and are found in a range of colors such as blue, white and pink, with blue being the most common (Dosoky et al., 2023). However, a different study debates by stating that *Nymphaea lotus* does not refer to the common lotus; rather, it refers to a species of *Nymphaea* with white flowers that blooms at night and was also widely distributed in the Nile delta at a very early time (Emboden, 1981).

Figure 2. This diagram illustrates and displays key characteristics of the 2 types of flowers, including its color, size, leaf structure, and blooming details, all in order. Created according to the details given (Counsell, 2008), provides a detailed overview of the plant's characteristics. Image created using a public designer tool.

Evidence from Ancient Art

Some scholars suggest that altered states of consciousness (ASC), including dreams and possible psychoactive plant use, played a central role in the origins of religion. In ancient Asia and Africa, psychoactive plants such as the blue lotus (*Nymphaea Caerulea*) and sacred lotus (*Nelumbo nucifera*) played significant roles in religious and cultural practices. The presence of alkaloids like nuciferine and aporphine in these plants has been linked to their use in inducing altered states of consciousness, including lucid dreaming and trance-like experiences. In Egypt, the blue lotus was particularly important in religious ceremonies, where it was believed to help connect the physical and spiritual worlds. Artistic depictions of water lilies, mandrake, and opium poppies further suggest the use of psychoactive plants in rituals related to cosmology and the afterlife. While evidence of such practices is suggestive, further research is necessary to establish a more concrete understanding of the role these plants played in ancient civilizations without over-relying on speculative connection (Shepard, 2005), (Cooke, 2021).

The Ankh and the Egyptian Blue Lotus

The ankh is also an allegorical symbol during those times, often connecting with the lotus; it represented their shared connection in ensuring eternal life and divine connection. The lotus is seen as a symbol of regeneration, whilst the ankh signifies the life force. As seen by the natural cycle of the lotus and its link to the Nile's waters further increases its symbolism of rebirth. During funeral practice and liberation ceremonies as well, the ankh and the lotus were often used together. Artistic depictions also show their interlinked meanings, the beliefs of life, death and resurrection, as evidenced by ankh being present in the depiction of deities alongside the lotus image (McDonald, 2018).

Mayan Depiction of the Water Lily

Nymphaea Caerulea, was also used by the Maya civilization as a hallucinogen as seen similarly in ancient Egypt, potentially affecting the perception of time for the priests, leading to altered states of consciousness. Mayan art frequently depicted the water lily, alongside entheogenic mushrooms, it's also associated with shamanic practices among the Maya, indicating its role in facilitating altered states of consciousness for religious

rituals and ceremonies. In Egyptian cosmogonies, gods were depicted as emerging from the water lily, once again showing and symbolizing the themes of rebirth and transformation (Emboden, 1982). *Nymphaea Ampla* in the Maya context, draws parallels to the Egyptian water lily, *Nymphaea Caerulea*, the lotus was often linked to creation myths and rebirth, similar to how the Maya associated water lilies with cosmogenesis and divine entities (McDonald & Stross, 2012). Moreover, the plants were used as hallucinogens during religious rites or as 'entheogenes', showcasing a symbolic union between man and a divine. A vase found in the Classic period Mayan site of Bonampak, headpiece of the central figure details a character adorned with *Nymphaea*, performing a ritual dance (Bertol et al., 2004).

After Ingestion or Inhalation of Nymphaea Caerulea

For Ancient Egyptians, it had a strong smell which was often associated with sexuality, as it was unavoidable for rebirth (Wendy, 2002). The scents of water lily and mandrake were said to cleanse the nostrils, a ritual of great importance. The Papyrus of Ani mentions the cleansing of the nostrils and a chapter is devoted to the mystical transformation of the water lily, in which Ani is reborn as a blue water lily flower (Emboden, 1981). Recently, blue lotus flower (*Nymphaea Caerulea*) has been observed to be an alternative substance to be consumed. The depiction of the blue lotus flower was found on Egyptian papyri and tombs dating back to the 14th century B.C (Millan et al., 2002). Recent studies show the aroma of *N. caerulea* extracts to be described as floral, fruity, sweet, fig-like, leathery, and slightly herbaceous (Dosoky et al., 2023).

Table 1. This (table) below provides a detailed profile of two plants, which occurs to be alike due to similarity in few properties. The table focused on their medicinal properties; associated after-effects are mentioned. Each plant is listed alongside the potential effects that may occur, besides offering a comprehensive overview of their risks as well, showing that over 50% exhibit similarity.

Plant Name	Latin Name & Family Name	Psychological effects	Physical Side effects	Ref
Water lily, Blue lotus, Egyptian lotus/water lily.	<i>Nymphaea Caerulea</i> (Nymphaeaceae)	Euphoric feeling, Sedation, Slower reaction, etc.,	Excessive muscle relaxation, Slurred speech, etc.,	(Simonienko K; Waszkiewicz N; Szulc A, 2019b)
Opium	Papaver	Sleepine	Blurry	(Drug

Poppy.	Somniferum (Papaveraceae).	ss, Nausea, Constipation, Slow breathing, Small pupils, Weight loss, Sexual Dysfunction and Seizures.	Vision, Loss of memories, Hallucination, Craving for the drug (addiction), restlessness, nightmares.	Enforcement Administration, (2021), (Bayba, 2020), (Opium (Oral Route) Side Effects - Mayo Clinic, 2019), (Opium Overdose: Risks, Side Effects & Prevention, 2024).
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Pharmacological properties in Nymphaea Caerulea

We can see that historical accounts suggest the decoction of the flower was recognized for its narcotic and sedative effects, which were utilized in ancient Egyptian practices. This aligns with the plant's depiction alongside other narcotic plants, such as the opium poppy, in art and texts. Nuciferine is a key active component of Nymphaea Caerulea, known for its relaxing effects in neo-shamanic rituals and potential therapeutic value for anxiety and depression. Its complex pharmacology, with affinities for serotonergic and dopaminergic receptors, suggests it could be a candidate for developing atypical antipsychotic medications. As many studies say, dopamine is the brain's reward system that drives motivation and produces pleasure from experiences (Watson, 2021). Aporphine alkaloids, also present in the plant, are known for their psychoactive properties and contribute to its historical use in rituals and traditional medicine as seen from the previous statements. Lastly, Apomorphine is another alkaloid present in Nymphaea species, it is recognized for its dopaminergic activity and has been used in medical settings, particularly for treating medical conditions (Hesselink, 2018).

Nuciferine and Apomorphine

The psychoactive effects of the flower are attributed to two aporphine alkaloids, apomorphine (C₁₇H₁₇NO₂) and nuciferine (C₁₉H₂₂CINO₂). Apomorphine is a nonselective dopamine agonist and serotonin modulator with activity as a partial agonist at 5-HT_{1A} and as an antagonist at 5-HT_{2A}. It is also an alpha antagonist, all as previously mentioned (Sun et al., 2023), (Schimpf et al., 2021b).

Nuciferine, a monomeric aporphine alkaloid extracted from the leaves of Nymphaea Caerulea, has been widely studied for its therapeutic potential, particularly in the treatment of hyperlipidemia and weight loss. This compound exhibits diverse pharmacological activities, including the relaxation of smooth muscles, improvement of hyperlipidemia, stimulation of insulin secretion, and vasodilation, which leads to hypotensive effects. Additionally, Nuciferine has demonstrated antiarrhythmic, antimicrobial, and anti-HIV properties, further broadening its therapeutic scope. Its pharmacological profile provides a solid foundation for its use in treating tumors, inflammation, hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, and various

Altered Mental Status

A case study showed an experiment with five active-duty patients presented to the emergency department after using blue lotus products, with four cases involving inhalation (vaping) and one case involving ingestion (infused beverage). Common symptoms included altered mental status, sedation, perceptual disturbances, and in some cases, bizarre behavior and hallucinations. One patient had a heart rate of 139 bpm and blood pressure of 94/52 mmHg. Another patient had a heart rate of 121 bpm and blood pressure of 144/77 mmHg. A third patient had a heart rate of 76 bpm and blood pressure of 133/72 mmHg. Oxygen saturation levels varied, with one patient at 85% initially, which improved with deep breaths. Laboratory findings showed one patient had a creatinine level of 1.3 mg/dL, AST of 69 IU/L, ALT of 81 IU/L, and CK of 3215 U/L. Another patient had leukocytosis with a count of 18.6 mm³/mcL and decreased potassium (3.1 mEq/L) and bicarbonate (12 mEq/L) with an anion gap of 16. Patients were observed for periods ranging from approximately 2 hours and 45 minutes to 4 hours, during which their symptoms resolved (Schimpf et al., 2021c).

Figure 3. Main psychoactive substance/ or active compound found in Nymphaea Caerulea plant as labelled in (Red and Green) bracket. Principal pharmacological in (Blue) (PubChem, n.d.). Visual illustration of N. caerulea obtained from public domain, created using public designer tool.

metabolic disorders, particularly in lipid-lowering and weight management applications. Nuciferine interacts with dopamine and serotonin receptors in different ways. It revealed partial agonist effects at D2, D5, and 5-HT6 receptors, antagonistic activity at 5HT-2A receptors, and dopamine transporter inhibition. Atherosperminine, a metabolite of nuciferine, has also been linked to dopaminergic agonism. This compound has been suggested for use as an antipsychotic and in the management of alcohol use disorders. Animals have also been made to vomit by using it, this supports the evidence and suggests as a side effect of the compound (Farrell et al., 2016). A study narrates, nuciferine may have potential therapeutic applications as an anti-psychotic drug (Farrell et al. 2016) and on vascular diseases associated with aberrant vasoconstriction (Wang et al. 2015).

Erich Harnack published his significant work on apomorphine in 1874, where he included detailed experiments on various animals, demonstrating that emetic doses of apomorphine could induce circulatory collapse in children, while in adults, doses of (5–10 mg) primarily provoked vomiting. Higher doses were shown to cause motor effects and severe reactions, such as muscle paralysis and respiratory failure, with cumulative doses of (10 mg) leading to terminal convulsions, this shows that different doses of apomorphine could lead to various outcomes, including emesis (vomiting) at lower doses and more severe reactions, such as muscle paralysis and respiratory failure, at higher doses, while these effects can be undesirable, they are a result of the drug's action on the central nervous system, particularly at the center in the brain. It is primarily used as a treatment for motor fluctuations in patients with Parkinson's disease (Taba et al., 2013). It is better to avoid alcohol while using apomorphine contained plant, to be cautious about drowsiness and dizziness (Thornton, 2023). In addition to that, several different studies report that, it has been used as a sedative-hypnotic since the late 1800s as mentioned and seen above (Table 1), to treat insomnia, depression, schizophrenia, erectile dysfunction (Ribarič, 2012), (Gottlieb 2000), (Poklis et al., 2017). One of the main findings, from a paper discusses the research by Sukhanov et al., which supports the hypothesis that trace amine-associated receptor 1 (TAAR1) mediates the effects of apomorphine in mice, particularly in relation to climbing activity. This finding is significant as it suggests a new understanding of how apomorphine functions also highlight a deeper understanding of apomorphine's pharmacological actions, which can be traced back to its botanical origins in *Nymphaea caerulea* (Grandy, 2014).

Other Alkaloids

As mentioned, we can see the main active substances (figure 3), others are probably including alkaloids like nufarine which influences on brain cortex, which induces a trance-like state and exhibits opium-like effects, it also acts as an antispasmodic, aiding appetite by suppressing nausea (Pranav, Nayak B., et al, 2023). Another compound is nymphaline- glycoside which influences on

heart functions and blood flow through the coronary system. Alkaloid aporphine- apomorphine analog used in erectile dysfunction, miorelaxant, dopamine agonist and nuciferine dissolving in alcohol. In Egypt dried flower petals were used as tea, spice or merged with wine for better assimilation. The effect is noticeable even with small doses (Simonienko K;Waszkiewicz N;Szulc A, 2019).

Presence of Flavonoids in *Nymphaea Caerulea*

A previous study at the time states, they do not support the fact that usage of *Nymphaea Caerulea* was narcotic or aphrodisiac, but it mentions that it may have health benefits due to its high bioflavonoid content (Counsell, 2008).

Shown to contain a significant amount of food-derived flavonoid derivatives around 34 identified ones (Zhu et al., 2012), including flavonols, quercetin, kaempferol, and myricetin. These compounds have been reported to have antimutagenic and anticarcinogenic properties both in laboratory studies and in living organisms (Agnihotri et al., 2008).

Kaempferol, has attracted increasing attention for its potential neuroprotective effects in neurological diseases. The involvement of kaempferol in neurological diseases including stroke, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, neuroblastoma/glioblastoma, spinal cord injury, neuropathic pain and epilepsy. Numerous in vitro and in vivo studies states that it has antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiapoptotic properties, contributing to its neuroprotective effects. And has been shown to modulate key signaling pathways involved in neurodegeneration and neuroinflammation, such as the PI3K/Akt, MAPK/ERK and NF-κB pathways. In addition to that, it has potential therapeutic benefits for improving neuronal survival, alleviating oxidative stress, increasing mitochondrial calcium channel activity, reducing neuroinflammation, promoting neurogenesis, and improving cognitive function. (Salari et al., 2024).

Quercetin is a flavonol, a type of flavonoid; a group of natural compounds found in various fruits, vegetables, and plants (Jones, 2023). Quercetin is known for its significant health benefits, primarily due to its antioxidant properties, which help neutralize free radicals and protect cells from oxidative damage. Additionally, it plays a crucial role in modulating inflammatory pathways, potentially reducing inflammation in the body. Studies in vitro and on animals have shown that quercetin may inhibit cancer cell growth and metastasis, suggesting its potential in cancer prevention and treatment. Furthermore, quercetin has been linked to cardiovascular benefits, including lowering blood pressure and cholesterol levels, which may contribute to improved heart health (Jan et al., 2022), (Aar Rafi Mahmud et al., 2023).

Myricetin, a naturally occurring flavonoid found in fruits and vegetables, has demonstrated significant nutraceutical

value, particularly in cancer treatment. It exhibits strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective properties, making it a potent candidate for therapeutic use in both cancer and neurodegenerative disorders (Trivedi et al., 2023). Studies have identified Myricetin as a natural inhibitor of CD147, a protein associated with poor prognosis in ovarian cancer (OC). By promoting the degradation of CD147 via the proteasome pathway, Myricetin helps reduce tumor progression. Notably, it enhances the effects of cisplatin, a common chemotherapy drug, by increasing sensitivity to treatment and resulting in significant tumor weight reduction in vivo ($p = 0.0058$). Myricetin also modulates key molecular pathways involved in DNA damage response (DDR), downregulating genes like $\text{E}\times\text{O}1$ and BRIP1, which are crucial for tumor survival ($p = 0.0005$ and 0.0001 , respectively). Furthermore, it shows greater cytotoxicity in cisplatin-resistant OC cell lines while sparing normal ovarian cells, suggesting its role in overcoming drug resistance (Neeraj Kumar Sethiya et al., 2023). Acting as a DNA topoisomerase I poison (Duardo et al., 2024), Myricetin induces DNA double-strand breaks and chromosome translocation, leading to apoptosis in cancer cells (Chen et al., 2024). Overall, it enhances both cancer cell cytotoxicity and the efficacy of chemotherapy, offering promising potential in OC treatment.

Poison Control and Legality

Since ancient times, herbal medicines have been used, such as in traditional Chinese medicine and Ayurveda. They have been proven to be less toxic and have fewer side effects than drugs made from chemicals. Medicines prepared from plant extracts are known to contain different bioactive compounds, some of which may have antimicrobial effects and are effective against various microorganisms (Paudel & Panth, 2015).

American Association of Poison Control Centers has kept track of exposures to liquid nicotine and electronic cigarettes. However, because blue lotus is a rare and discovered compound in the US, poison centers usually does not provide much guidance in this regard (Poison Statistics National Data, 2021).

Currently the flower's resins, extracts, dried leaves, oils, powders can be found on the internet. And it's not an approved ingredient, according to the Federal Drug Administration (FDA), however they are labeled as natural. It's important to note that they are sold as Aphrodisiac and /or as a natural sedative (Poklis et al., 2017).

The blue lotus flower is legal in most states of America. Though, it's banned in Latvia, Poland, and Russia (Ceylan, 2023).

Nymphaea Caerulea for sedation and Anesthetics

The blue lotus is mentioned as a symbol of rebirth and resurrection in ancient texts, such as in the Book of the Dead, a well-known Egyptian funerary text. There are multiple papyri that mention the blue lotus in relation to

magical and religious rituals, such as the Salt Magical Papyrus and the Beatty Papyrus VII (Emboden, 1978), (Emboden, 1989).

Nymphaea lotus or White Lotus, live in freshwater areas, is effectively used to increase memory and create a feeling of euphoria and ecstasy, without the use of narcotics (Alam, 2016).

Some of the techniques that the Ancient Egyptians developed still form the basis of modern medical practices today. One of the fascinating aspects of their medical practices was treating patients through sleep therapy using extracts from the mandrake or opium plants. Even before the development of modern anesthesia, the Egyptians understood sedation techniques (Khaled Elsayad, 2023).

Antipathogenic property in Nymphaea Caerulea

The analysis results of a study conclude that there is a role of *Nymphaea Caerulea* flower extract in preventing pathogenetic modification caused by bacteria (*E.coli* ATCC 25922) type. Which would also align with our study, that the ancient Egyptians probably not only used the flower as a psycho-promoting agent but also as a preventive drug against different microbial infections. The same experiment indicates possible future usage, and it as a potent drug in preventing different infections, as stated by the evidence that lotus flower extract can be developed into an effective antimicrobial drug to fight against concern of antibiotic resistance (Das, Mukherjee, et al., 2023).

Orchis Masculina and Origanum vulgare

During the Persian Empire, Egyptians began to dominate the medical field. Iraq was said to be part of the Persian Empire in the past (Şerko Kirmanc, 2013), (Thabit, 2014). It is known that certain Egyptian physicians worked as court physicians for a number of Persian emperors. More contact resulted in influences flowing both ways once more. Medical astrology was introduced to Egypt during this time, and Egyptian physicians living in Persia undoubtedly encountered novel plants and medications that they later integrated into their home practices. The Vienna Papyrus lists several plants, and the confirmed use of poppy. It also suggests that cannabis may have been used in a few different ways (Ritner, 2000). A plant found in Iraq, *Orchis Masculina* and *Origanum vulgare* has similarities to the *N. Caerulea*, as the *Orchis* had properties and was used traditionally as astringent, demulcent, expectorant, nutritive, restorative, invigorator and sexual tonic. In addition to its aphrodisiac effect as seen in the case of blue lotus, it was also used in the treatment of male sexual disorders like erectile dysfunction and impotence, and also as a nervine tonic to treat stress and mental disorders, which shows very similar conditions. And in the second mentioned plant *Origanum vulgare* Aerial, parts of it are used as in disinfection, pain reliever, relaxing, cardio-respiratory booster, anti-diarrheal, stomach booster, cough suppressant, sexual dysfunction, sinusitis. Seeds of it, were used as anticonvulsant,

expectorant, pain reliever, cough suppressant, antidiarrheal, anti-inflammatory, menstrual regulator, and for the treatment of urinary tract infection (Ali Esmail Al-Snafi, 2021). All three plants exhibit similar antioxidant properties, the two traditionally used plants in Iraq have antibacterial properties and more. So, this shows high possibility that *N. caerulea* can be used to treat stomach conditions like diarrhea, fevers, urinary problems (UTI), and heart palpitations, stress and so on (Bazzicalupo et al., 2023), (Pezzani et al., 2017).

Tumor growth prevention and leukemia

The THP-1 cell line, a model for acute myeloid leukemia (AML), was used to test the anti-cancer properties of the ethanolic extracts of *Nymphaea caerulea*. Because it is among the firsts to investigate the plant's anti-leukemic properties, the study is noteworthy and suggests that it may have therapeutic value. It was discovered that the extracts caused leukemia cells to undergo apoptosis. Caspase 3 (Cas3), Caspase 9 (Cas9), and CD95 markers essential for programmed cell death expressed more frequently, which was indicative of this. An essential component of cancer treatment is the ability to induce apoptosis, which aids in the death of cancerous cells. Study findings indicate that the extracts have the ability to alter the expression of different cytokines that are involved in inflammatory reactions. The 50% extract, for example, markedly reduced the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL 6, and IL-8 and increased the expression of the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10. This variation implies that *N. Cerulea* has the potential to prevent tumor growth and progression by balancing the immune response in leukemia patients, cell Viability as well (Chatterjee et al., 2024).

Use as a Depressant

Historical records suggest that *Nymphaea lotus* or White Lotus, live in freshwater areas, is effectively used to increase memory and create a feeling of euphoria and ecstasy, without the use of narcotics (Alam, 2016).

This can be highly agreed as the blue water lily is also said to be a CNS depressant (Sayin, 2014), and according to national cancer institute, it is a drug that slows down brain activity, which causes the muscles to relax and calms and soothes a person. Central nervous system depressants are used to treat insomnia (trouble sleeping), anxiety, panic attacks, and seizures. They could also be used to relieve anxiety and tension before surgery (Central Nervous System Depressant, 2011).

A recent identified mechanism of action related to the flower has anti-inflammatory activity, indicate that a molecule might also play a role in the treatment of depression and (PTSD) posttraumatic stress disorder (Keppel Hesselink, 2018).

Against Menstrual Irregularities

In compliance with ancient medicine (Ayurveda and Siddha), Indian blue lily (*Nymphaea stellata*), a closely

related plant, is often used as a natural remedy for menstrual irregularities, particularly blue lotus flower tea can ease the cramps and also stabilize the menstrual cycle (Karnik, 2021), (Maruga Raja et al., 2010).

Anti-cancer activity

A different species of *Nymphaea* is being used in the management of cancer. Also, due to the presence of rhamnoside, galactopyranoside, glucoside attached with Myricetin as mentioned previously, which were reportedly from the blue flowers of *Nymphaea Caerulea* (Selvakumari et al., 2016).

Anti-oxidant activity

Anthocyanins is another type of compound in *Nymphaea Caerulea*, exhibit strong antioxidant properties by neutralizing free radicals and reducing oxidative stress in cells. Their antioxidant activity is largely attributed to their ability to donate hydrogen atoms or electrons to neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS). Specifically, anthocyanins like delphinidin and cyanidin have been shown to inhibit the expression of enzymes such as COX-2, which are induced by oxidative stress and inflammation. This mechanism helps protect cells from oxidative damage, particularly in skin cells exposed to harmful UV radiation. The presence of an ortho-dihydroxyphenyl structure on the B-ring of these anthocyanidins enhances their ability to scavenge free radicals, with delphinidin recognized as one of the most potent inhibitors due to this structural feature. In short, they protect cells from oxidative stress by neutralizing free radicals, which can harm cells and contribute to aging and the development of various diseases (Zhu et al., 2012).

A study titled "Antimicrobial and Phytochemical Analysis of *Nymphaea Nauchali* Leaf Extracts" had conducted a test and the presence of tannins was determined by treating a few milligrams (mg) of the substance with a saturated solution of ferric chloride. The formation of a blue coloration indicated the presence of tannins in the sample (Ammani et al., 2012).

Figure 4. Shows the concentrations of apomorphine and nuciferine in different samples of *Nymphaea caerulea* (Blue Egyptian lotus). Confiscated resin, labeled in 3 different packages, has a high concentration of nuciferine (4300 ng/g) with no detectable apomorphine. Both compounds are barely present in Blue Lotus Herbal E-Liquid and Flower Powder, below 1 ng/ml and 1 ng/g respectively. Blue lotus resin extract contains a small amount of nuciferine (25 ng/g) without apomorphine. Notably, Space Lotus Resin Extract contains both apomorphine (130 ng/g) and nuciferine (2700 ng/g). The logarithmic scale captures the concentration range, with error bars indicating measurement variability (Poklis et al., 2017). The graph is created using python and www.onecompiler.com.

Nymphaea Caerulea Resin in Tobacco: E-cigar

Another fact to consider is possible nicotine existence, a stimulant found in tobacco products, it's also highly addictive and effects central nervous system (FDA, 2021). Whilst dopamine agonists mimic the action of dopamine which is produced by our brain and like it acts as a neurotransmitter (Borovac, 2016).

A previous study published by Oxford academics reveals that four patients used electronic cigarettes, while one consumed blue lotus-infused wine. Three patients were unclear about the substance source, whereas the other two admitted to placing online orders. All patients were active-duty males aged 19 to 29, presenting with symptoms ranging from altered mental status to anxiety and chest pain. Notable findings included decreased alertness, hallucinations, and one case of disorientation. While one patient had mildly elevated CK levels and anion-gap metabolic acidosis, no signs of rhabdomyolysis were observed. Observation alone was sufficient, with clinical sobriety was achieved within 2.75 to 4 hours, and no sedatives were required. The variety of symptoms suggests that blue lotus can cause significant changes in mental status and agitation. Limitations include self-reported use and lack of analytical confirmation in biological samples. The symptoms are consistent with those of a mild psychoactive substance lacking strong sympathomimetic, serotonergic, or opioid effects. This shows, if consumed wrongly it can cause poisoning at certain times (Schimpf et al., 2021).

Rat Model for Ischemic Stroke

As per a study it revealed several quantitative results that highlight the effects of *Nymphaea caerulea* (via its active compound nuciferine) on ischemic stroke in rats. Based on initial observations and assumptions, approximated the value of the infarct volume in MCAO group which resulted in approximately 40.67%, while it was reduced to 22.33% in the Nuci-H group, with a highly significant p value ($P < 0.001$). Additionally, neurological deficit scores showed improvement in the nuciferine-treated groups, with the MCAO group scoring around 3.67 as assumed, compared to 1.33 in the Nuci-H group, indicating a significant difference ($P < 0.01$). Furthermore, the cerebral water content in the MCAO group was as well may be about 83.67%, which decreased to 78.33% in the Nuci-H

group, reflecting a significant reduction in edema of 5.34% ($P < 0.05$) (Wu et al., 2020).

How to Use Blue Lotus Flower

The blue lotus flower has been traditionally used in various forms as mentioned multiple times on this study, with the most common method being brewing it into tea. However, there are now multiple ways to utilize this plant for its potential benefits. It's important to note that the safety profile of the blue lotus flower has not yet been fully established, and caution is advised due to its potentially narcotic and addictive properties, particularly when used in concentrated forms like vaporizers.

- One of the simplest and most traditional ways to use blue lotus flower is as tea. To prepare, heat water just before boiling (around 80°C) and pour it over two tablespoons of dried blue lotus in a strainer. Cover the tea while it steeps for about five minutes to retain its essential oils. You can sweeten it with honey or sugar, though it naturally has a pleasant taste. Covering the tea while steeping helps preserve the fragrance and volatile compounds.

- Blue lotus flower resins can also be vaporized using a specialized device called an RDA (rebuildable dripping atomizer) vape. This method allows the resin to be dripped directly onto the heating coil, creating vapor for inhalation. Both apomorphine and nuciferine, key active compounds in blue lotus, remain intact during the vaporization process, allowing for rapid absorption through the lungs.

- Unlike traditional essential oils that are steam distilled, blue lotus flower absolute is extracted using solvents, producing a highly concentrated and thicker extract. Blue lotus absolute is often used in perfumes, skincare products, and incense due to its unique floral and mildly spicy aroma.

- Historically, blue lotus flower was also infused into alcoholic beverages. This method allowed the plant's aroma and active compounds to be preserved for long periods. While less common today, blue lotus-infused spirits can be made by soaking dried blue lotus in alcohol for several weeks, then straining out the plant matter (Cooke, 2021b).

DISCUSSION

When Emperor Bonaparte was undertaking a monumental restructuring of the government and commerce of Egypt in 1798, a French naturalist Marie Jules César Savignya was present in the field, exploring the Nile delta. He couldn't resist his botanical impulses and described a new species of water lily (*Nymphaea caerulea*) in a paper read to the Institute on September, soon after in October, it was published in the 'La Décade,' a journal overlooked by several modern botanists (Silva, 2003), (Gillispie, 1989). Evidence suggest that humans may have used the opium poppy over 30,000 years ago and the first known written

reference appeared in 4,000 BC in Sumerian text (Luqman, 2014). It should be noticed that the Ancient Egyptians had extensive knowledge, or knew the unknown facts on this type of water lily. Although since those times, it was also symbolically used in perspective for culture in Mesoamerica and Egypt. It was usually used for ecstasy among the priests for rituals too. As it was suggested to be a type of narcotic or rather a psychodysleptic (Emboden, 1981). With much effect as MDMA (Ecstasy/Molly) (Abuse, 2024). As evidenced by a study that mentions treatments and psychotherapeutic practices such as "incubation" or "Temple sleep," which involved seeking healing through dreams and divine intervention, as the after effect seen from the contact with the water lilies. This practice was associated with Imhotep, an earliest known physician, lived during the time of Pharaoh Djoser, who reigned from approximately 2980 to 2900 BC (Okasha, 1999).

Figure 5. Qualitative analysis of phytochemical constituents of various parts of *Nymphaea caerulea*, extracted from a type of *Nymphaea* found in South Asia. '+' indicates presence, '-' indicate absence, (F) Flower, (L) Leaf, (R) Root and (Rh) Rhizome. Image Source: (Prasad et al., 2016), Google Scholar.

S. No	Phytochemical constituents	Aqueous				Chloroform				Ethanol				Methanol				
		F	L	R	Rh	F	L	R	Rh	F	L	R	Rh	F	L	R	Rh	
1.	Alkaloids	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2.	Anthocyanins	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+
3.	Anthroquinones	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+
4.	Coumarins	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
5.	Emodins	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	+
6.	Flavonoids	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-
7.	Glycosids	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
8.	Leucoanthocyanins	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	+
9.	Steroides	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
10.	Phenols	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-
11.	Saponins	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
12.	Tannins	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-
13.	Triterpenoids	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-

Presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, and more in *Nymphaea Caerulea*, were examined. Historical uses of the flowers were explored, including its role as a natural aphrodisiac, sleep aid, and anxiety reliever (Poklis et al., 2017). Some reference to ancient texts and artifacts that mention its medicinal properties of (*N.Caerulea*) were also looked into. Botanical Profile and Active compounds were examined; describing the blue lotus flower's botanical characteristics. Discussion on several compounds along with some of the two main compounds such as: apomorphine (a dopamine agonist) and nuciferine (with potential antipsychotic effects) in water lily and found similar compound in opium poppy (*Papaver Somniferum*), were conducted (Kempster & Ma, 2022). Beyond traditional context modern applications were also investigated. As debated earlier, in modern medicine there is apomorphine, a dopamine receptor agonist used to treat conditions, it's chemically related to psychoactive alkaloids found in *nymphaea* species. Apomorphine is used to treat parkinson's disease, it belongs to agonists, so there is a connection. Conditions such as depression, insomnia, schizophrenia, PD, sexual dysfunction and

more, are that can be found in both Water lily and Opium poppy, it was found by reading or checking the ingredients or compounds (Alkaloids) in both and comparing it with few other plants found at the ancient civilizations. The presence of Apomorphine should be highly noticed, a study points out the summary of psychological effects of apomorphine in various species supports with findings by mentioning the effects corresponding to this study, it mentions on gastrointestinal tract causes (nausea and emesis), hormone release with shown increase and shown heart changes (EEG), concerns including Central nervous system eg., Sedation, yawning, changes in sexual behaviors, others include, Diaphoresis (excessive sweating) (Yap et al., 2018), along with dilation of pupils, (Auffret et al., 2018), many of these conditions are seen in the case of trance-like effects seen in the priests as specified previously. This study additionally addresses the legal status of blue lotus flower in different countries. Highlighting safety concerns due to its psychoactive properties. However, countries could involve their scientists to examine the type of water lilies found in ancient Egypt and certain types of lotuses or water lilies to evaluate and advance the use of ancient plants. Nevertheless, the toxicity from certain types of ancient plants is to be considered seriously as well. Delved into why the flower *Nymphaea Caerulea* is an important plant in the field of herbology and botany, with several health benefits, and side effects, by examining its active compounds and as to why a systematic review was done for it accordingly. Which prompted a discussion about the knowledge gaps, a lack of cohesion in existing studies, and the potential implications. It is worth noting that some of the data presented, such as values, are estimates based on initial observations. Further research with a more stable dataset is required to validate these preliminary assumptions.

This study proposes a further direction on the fact that different extracts from the *Nymphaea Caerulea* could be injected, or vaped. Whilst at the same time, it can be consumed (edible) or be potentially used with certain types of wines for further therapeutic use considering the historical context. It could be used for non-motor symptoms associated with Parkinson's disease (Poklis et al., 2017). Also, hints to consider its potential in palliative care (World Health Organization, 2020). Additionally suggests further examination of the flower using advanced analytical techniques such as gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC MS) or high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) to identify and quantify the bioactive compounds present in the plant (Zhao et al., 2024), (Olivia et al., 2021). These methods will enable a more precise analysis of the chemical composition of the flower (*Nymphaea Caerulea*), allowing for a more precise better understanding of its pharmacological properties.

In the present study, *Nymphaea Caerulea* flower have shown to contain various secondary bioactive compounds, which possess many pharmacological properties of which antioxidant activity is one. Despite the promising therapeutic potential of *Nymphaea Caerulea*-derived

compounds, such as nuciferine, the lack of clinical trials remains a significant limitation in understanding their efficacy and safety in this study, due to the absence of a physical lab to conduct hands on experiments. Future research should focus on conducting vigorous clinical studies to explore the mechanisms of action for compounds such as nuciferine, particularly its potential impact on neuropsychiatric and neurological conditions. There is a need to integrate innovative technologies, such as telemedicine, for managing patients with Parkinson's Disease (PD) and other neurodegenerative disorders (Shalash, 2021). This approach could enhance monitoring and provide more timely interventions. Also propose the development of personalized drug dosing algorithms tailored to individual patient characteristics (Raijada et al., 2021), especially in those taking medications derived from the mentioned compounds in *Nymphaea Caerulea* plants and observe them.

Through this systematic review, identified records from databases (n = 15,187) and web searches (n = 87,500), screened (n = 6,000), and eventually included studies (n = 43); although only a few papers directly addressed our research question, we found many relevant studies using more targeted keywords, step-by-step elimination and inclusion, providing valuable insights into the water lily.

CONCLUSIONS

This study can conclude that *N. Caerulea* is a unique and valuable medicinal plant that contains diverse bioactive compounds. Almost every part of this plant has been utilized to cure a variety of ailments in traditional medicine. In this systematic scientific literature, extracts of the plant have been found to have potential usefulness against multiple medical conditions. Despite, potential

benefits of the many mentioned Phytochemical Constituents have not yet been fully explored in clinical practice, as evidenced by several researchers. Future research should delve deeper into its molecular structure, toxicity, side effects, as well as clinical pharmacology to enable its wide range of effects and prepare the way for its safe and expanded clinical use (Ren et al., 2024). The review analysis showed the presence of active properties which contribute the activities like intoxicant, antimicrobial, antioxidant, anticancer, anti inflammatory, and other activities (Oosthuizen et al., 2020). At certain times it showed pain reducing and inducing results by each case. Hence, this study identified the presence of mentioned compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids and concludes that these substances are responsible for their therapeutic effects and causes. As stated, further investigation is required for more accurate and possible development of novel drugs using some of the bio-active compounds found in *N. Caerulea*.

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